

STRATEGIES TO CONSOLIDATE THE SCHOOL – FAMILY - COMMUNITY EDUCATIONAL PARTNERSHIP, IN THE CONTEXT OF CONTEMPORARY SOCIETAL CHALLENGES*

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Abstract

The present study aims to investigate the issue of optimizing the partnership relationship school - family - community as a prerequisite for effective collaboration among all entities involved in this relationship. The general objective of the research is to analyze the collaborative dimensions of the three investigated components and to highlight the extent to which these relationships contribute to, or hinder, the individual's preparation for successful school, family, and community integration.

Sociocultural and educational events increasingly demonstrate the necessity of cooperation at all levels: familial, educational, community, regional, and global. Partnership-based and collaboration-based interactions are progressively oriented toward mutual understanding, interpersonal connection, and effective communication, becoming more open and focused on the meaningful use of human resources.

In this context, we consider that, within contemporary society, education is no longer the exclusive responsibility of the school. In order to ensure the harmonious development of the child, close cooperation among school, family, and community — as well as other educational factors — is essential. These relationships and partnerships play a fundamental role in creating an educational climate favorable to learning and to the balanced development of students' personalities.

Key words: *Educational partnership, School–family–community collaboration, Community partners, parenting.*

1. Introductory theoretical considerations

The term partnership is defined as the association of two or more partners and, in the specialized literature, partnership represents the formal or informal manner in which two or more parties decide to act together in order to achieve a common goal (Cucoş, 2009). The educational partnership has increasingly become a central concept in the flexible and open curricular approach to educational issues. According

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to several researchers, the educational partnership is defined as a form of communication, cooperation, and collaboration among educational agents aimed at supporting the child in the process of personality development (Băran Pescaru, 2004). The educational agents may include parents, managers, teachers, psychologists, and members of the community (such as representatives of the Church, police institutions, NGOs, etc.) (Tabita, 2023).

Within the curricular approach to education, there is an identified need for understanding, respecting, and valuing diversity. Consequently, the educational partnership represents both a socio-human phenomenon and a pedagogical process of collaboration among social actors who, through interaction, support the efforts of the educational institutions and families, while contributing to the holistic development of the student's personality and ensuring the effectiveness of their social integration (Braghiș, 2013).

The development, coordination, and implementation of educational partnership projects have a profound impact on the construction and shaping of students' personalities and entail several advantages, including:

- the capitalization and development of the interests and aptitudes of those involved
- the organization of students' leisure time in an enjoyable and relaxing manner;
- the recreational nature of these forms of activity organization, while simultaneously pursuing educational objectives;
- the creation of collaborative relationships;
- the provision of a new framework for the development of the student's personality;
- the stimulation of critical thinking;
- the cultivation of multicultural awareness and perception.

The school–family partnership represents a form of pedagogical partnership, a concept recently introduced into the field of education, which “reflects the transformations recorded at the level of relationships established among the institutions directly and/ or indirectly involved in the design and implementation of the objectives of the educational system: the school, the family, the local community, social agents (economic, cultural, political, religious, etc.), social assistance factors, and others” (Cristea, 2000, p. 280).

Specialized literature (Epstein, 2009; 2010) highlights the significant role of parental involvement in collaboration with the school regarding children's development and education, while also emphasizing the benefits generated for parents, teachers, and the community. Nevertheless, educational practice—particularly within mainstream schools and especially in schools located in disadvantaged environments—reveals the existence of cultural, psychological, and social barriers that hinder not only effective collaboration among school, family, and community in the benefit of children, but often even minimal communication among these actors. A key role in consolidating school–family–community interactions is played by educational counseling services through the network of psycho-pedagogical assistance centers and counseling offices.

2. Main Theories and Paradigms Concerning School–Family–Community Relationships

Starting from the benefits that partnerships with educational stakeholders may bring to schools and students, it is necessary for school managers to implement strategies aimed at establishing the institution's priorities, attracting and raising awareness among interested actors regarding their role in promoting quality education, encouraging the direct participation of parents and representatives of local communities in the activity of consultative and governing bodies of general education institutions, and involving them in extracurricular activities. The development and implementation of such strategies require the prior preparation of the school's human resources for dialogue, mutual understanding, and collaboration (Orîndaş, 2019).

McAllister Swap (1993) describes four models for the development of relationships between parents and professionals (the protective model, the transmission model, the curriculum enrichment model, and the partnership model). These models are grounded in conscious and unconscious beliefs, expectations, and strategies that shape interactions between parents and professionals.

The McAllister Swap's protective model describes the power relationship established between families and institutions. The primary objective of this model is the prevention of conflict between parents and professionals. Parents are expected to transfer responsibility for their children's education to the educational institution and to adopt a non-interventionist position with regard to educational objectives. Consequently, the protective model may be understood as a model of separation, in which each participant is responsible solely for their own sphere of action. A major consequence of such a relationship is the discontinuity of educational efforts directed toward the child. When this form of relationship is examined from the perspective of the well-being of all participants involved, as the ultimate aim of cooperation, it becomes evident that it does not facilitate the achievement of a common objective. The lack of communication between parents and educators may therefore contribute to the absence of a shared perception regarding the existence of common goals.

It is widely acknowledged that the family environment plays a crucial role in a child's overall development. Therefore, educational institutions have assumed the role of correcting family education, which is often regarded as deficient and therefore in need of intervention. The institution positions itself as an educational authority in relation to parents, based on the assumption of parental ignorance and, implicitly, the need for guidance and instruction. According to McAllister Swap, this perspective is reflected in the transmission model. Although this model includes parents, it is fundamentally based on compliance with the educational objectives prescribed by educational institutions. Parents are perceived as lacking competence; therefore, they are expected to be educated in order to promote the values endorsed by the institution. Other authors, in more recent studies published over the last decade, argue that this approach fails to respect differences among families, as the relationship tends to impose uniform expectations upon all parents. This model emphasizes the need for communication between teachers and parents; however, the

communication itself remains unidirectional, namely from teachers to parents. Furthermore, although this model presupposes contact between the family and the institution, it cannot yet be considered genuine collaboration (Jevtic, 2023).

The paradigm of cooperation, which has been present in parent–educator relationships since the 1980s, is based on partnership, collaboration, and mutual respect. This paradigm starts from the premise that children are the shared responsibility of both parents and society, and that educational institutions should support and assist parents in their parenting efforts. The approach is founded on respect, appreciation, and acceptance of parents. This relationship acknowledges an individualized approach to each family, respect for diverse educational practices, and recognition of different cultures (family and institutional). The contribution of all participants involved in this relationship becomes visible through the quality of communication, clearly defined expectations, and mutual support. Two models proposed by McAllister Swap correspond to the interactions described above: the curriculum enrichment model and the partnership model. In the case of the curriculum enrichment model, the emphasis is placed on cooperation between parents and professionals in order to improve curricular objectives and content, with all participants in the process being treated with respect and equality.

The partnership model is based almost entirely on Bronfenbrenner’s ecological theory (1986), according to which various communities directly or indirectly influence the child, making their interaction particularly important. Although, similarly to the curriculum enrichment model, this approach emphasizes appreciation, respect, and mutual support, it differs through the extension of the partner culture to all communities surrounding the child (McAllister Swap, 1993). In this way, a new culture is constructed, one that integrates the family, peers, and the broader social culture within which the child develops.

Epstein (2001) made a major contribution to understanding parental involvement in children’s education. Her typology of parental involvement has become a widely used theoretical framework in educational research. According to Epstein, parents may be involved in six domains: Type 1: Parenting; Type 2: Communication; Type 3: Volunteering; Type 4: Learning at home support; Type 5: Decision-making; Type 6: Collaborating with the community.

By providing a stimulating environment, parents influence their children’s well-being, which indirectly affects their functioning within preschool settings. From Epstein’s perspective, however, parenting as involvement refers to parental characteristics. It is about the type of involvement that naturally emerges from the parental role itself. The explicit importance of parental education quality is not directly emphasized in this model. Nevertheless, teachers may contribute to children’s development by strengthening parents’ educational competencies (Sandberg, Vuorinen, 2008).

Parents’ own educational experiences play an essential role in shaping their later involvement in their children’s schooling. Internal working models developed during childhood influence parental perceptions, expectations, and behaviors. Parents who experienced positive educational trajectories are generally more inclined to actively

support their children's school activities, whereas negative experiences may generate reluctance or distrust toward educational institutions. Parental involvement should therefore be understood as a continuous and active process rather than occasional participation in school activities. Schools are required to develop strategies for attracting and engaging parents, creating welcoming contexts, and recognizing their essential role in the educational process (Merlău, 2020).

Most theories conclude that the dimensions of parental involvement in children's lives in relation to community participation have not changed significantly in recent years. However, public perspectives on how parental involvement should be approached have shifted from macroscopic interpretations toward more microscopic and emotionally centered approaches, moving beyond simple helping behaviors toward greater attention to children's feelings and emotional needs (Lai, Wu, 2024).

Parental involvement is strongly associated with improved academic performance, increased motivation, and enhanced interpersonal skills (Cuznețov, 2002). To leverage these benefits, educational institutions can establish efficiency-oriented intervention and working groups that actively engage families in school life and community development. Collaborative initiatives—such as ecological activities, anti-bullying campaigns, cyberbullying prevention programs, and social inclusion projects—can be co-facilitated by teachers and parents to foster students' civic, intercultural, and socio-educational competencies. Furthermore, organizing interactive workshops and community events can strengthen these stakeholder relationships, ultimately aligning the educational process with the demands of contemporary society (Cox-Peterson, 2011).

Patrikakou (2015) argues that in the context of increasing technologization, schools can develop confidential online progress reports reflecting students' educational achievements while also providing remedial or enrichment interventions. Digital workshops and online courses may be organized in partnership with IT companies to promote the foundations of digital education. Such partnerships may also involve students themselves, who are future adults living in an increasingly hyper-technologized society (Bryan, 2005).

Bryan and Epstein identified the central purpose of collaboration among educational agents (school – family – community) as the establishment of partnerships through which teachers cooperate with families and community members in order to help students succeed academically (Marinescu, 2023; Țibu, Goia, 2014).

3. Forms and strategies of educational partnership among school – family - community

There are numerous forms, methods, and strategies for implementing educational partnerships among family, school, and community. Their diversity can be explained by the existence of various theories regarding the role and necessity of family involvement in school and community life, as well as community participation in school activities. In reality, the relationships among family, school,

and community are complex and multidimensional, generating a wide variety of practical approaches and interpretations. Educational partnerships are developed progressively through concrete, planned, and systematically evaluated activities involving all relevant actors and explicitly targeting the improvement of students' educational experiences.

Starting from Joyce Epstein's model (1995; 2001; 2011) (one of the most frequently cited and internationally applied frameworks, also presented above), the following taxonomy of concrete forms of collaboration among family, school, and community may be identified: type I: parent workshops, home-support guides, home visits; type II: meetings, newsletters, digital platforms, individual consultations; type III: parents and community members involved in school activities; type IV: homework involving family participation and community research projects; type V: school councils, parent committees, public consultations; type VI: partnerships with NGOs, companies, cultural institutions, and social services.

According to J. Comer (1999), the core of the communication program consists of collaborative work conducted through three major teams: the parent and community actor team, the school planning and management team, and the student support and leadership team. The program includes students, school managers, teachers, and families working together within interconnected systems. However, this model has been criticized for insufficiently addressing the social, cultural, and political dimensions of these interactions (Orîndaş, 2019).

Based on the specific functions of school-family-community partnerships identified in the literature, Bryan and Holcomb McCoy (2004) propose several forms of collaboration, including mentoring programs, parent centers, volunteering programs, classroom assistance opportunities, home-visit programs, parent education programs, business partnerships, and school management and tutoring programs.

According to the thematic network model proposed by Jennifer Attride-Stirling, parental involvement consists of three dimensions (Ho, Tan, Ko et al.): interaction with the child, availability and responsibility for the child. Essential elements of parental involvement include: the importance of providing a positive role model; engaging children in outdoor activities; perceiving education as a means of socio-economic development for children (Orîndaş, 2019).

A more detailed inventory of the forms and methods of educational partnership (and communication) among school – family - community is provided by Larisa Cuzneţov (2018). Among others, the author proposes: a portfolio for each parent group; individual notebooks for each student; traditional parent meetings, alongside alternative forms of collaboration (parental education workshops; round tables; parent lectures); as well as the involvement of parents in cognitive and educational activities within the instructional process (classroom organization, the preparation of teaching materials, the planning and implementation of extracurricular activities, participation in psycho-pedagogical discussions, involvement in decisions concerning the organization of the educational process, the acquisition of children's literature); the creation of mobile informational stands or parent "bulletins" etc.; mobile classroom display panels.

Other categories of activities aim specifically at developing parental competencies (parent workshops, training sessions organized for parents and community agents, ice-breaking activities designed for initial meetings with parents, psycho-pedagogical counseling, guidance and information regarding periodic or permanent support services, round tables, lesson observations, school newsletters, public recognition of exemplary children and families, announcements regarding upcoming activities, and open-door events. Furthermore, discussions may be organized with school administrators, teaching staff, school psychologists, and other invited specialists; schools may also present formal school–family collaboration agreements specifying the responsibilities of schools, community actors, and parents within the educational partnership process.

Additional forms, methods, techniques and means of involving families and community members in the educational process (Cuznețov, 2018), include: short discussions with parents and students, written notices and concise communication notes, records of meetings with parents, developmental notes regarding children or other relevant subjects (daily schedule information, volunteer sign-up lists), reports, suggestions for continuing educational tasks at home, home visits designed to promote dialogue between school and family, consultation councils (composed of family and community members may also contribute to the planning of celebrations, events; excursions and visits; community collaborations; classroom maintenance activities etc.), the establishment of parent and community training centers, including community agents—special spaces (where parents may access books, articles, and journals concerning child education and development).

It becomes evident that the presence of families in the classroom is approached as a form of collective educational engagement. By assisting children within classroom activities, parents gain a deeper understanding of the educational processes taking place at school. Encouraging family participation in such activities motivates parents to support teachers more actively, particularly because many appreciate being directly involved in the educational environment attended by their own children. In the classroom, the appreciation and recognition of family members' contributions have beneficial effects not only on the broader community but also on children's academic progress and community integration.

In this context, (Cuznețov, 2018) several proposes regarding the participation of parents and other adults in classroom and community activities can be made: expressing gratitude to each parent for their support; providing specially designated spaces where parents may leave personal belongings or rest; creating informational posters for parent volunteers; awarding diplomas or certificates of appreciation for parents' contributions to classroom and school activities etc.

In conclusion, some educational institutions work systematically toward optimizing partnerships with families and communities, while others remain at an early stage of development, making gradual adjustments and rapid progress in order to support children, families, schools, and local communities more effectively.

4. Experimental–applied dimension

Following a micro-research study, the need for the development and effective implementation of partnership projects was identified. Such initiatives are desired by families, schools, and community representatives alike, with the aim of reducing the cognitive dissonance experienced by students who function simultaneously within these environments. Responses were collected from 87 participants distributed across four categories of educational roles, coming from educational institutions located in both urban and rural areas. A simple questionnaire consisting of 12 items was administered through Google forms (part of the Google Docs Editors Suite, completed online in an asynchronous format over a clearly established period of time).

The primary *purpose* of the family–school–community partnership was identified as the effective collaboration among the main educational actors meant to ensure students’ harmonious development, improve academic performance, and facilitate social integration. Through this partnership, the creation of an educational environment based on communication, mutual support, and active participation in the instructional process is pursued.

Specific Objectives

- Increasing parental involvement in students’ curricular and extracurricular school activities;
- Improving communication among teachers, families, and community representatives;
- Developing an educational environment based on respect, cooperation, and responsibility;
- Capitalizing on community resources in support of educational activities;
- Preventing school dropout and risk behaviors through collaborative activities;
- Supporting students’ personal and social development through integrated educational programs;
- Promoting equal opportunities and social inclusion within the school environment.

Research Hypotheses

H.1. If there is permanent collaboration among family, school, and community, then students’ academic performance will improve.

H.2. The use of community resources in educational activities organized by schools, with parental participation, facilitates students’ social integration and the development of their competencies.

H.3. Effective communication between teachers and families contributes to the rapid identification and resolution of students’ difficulties and supports positive community integration.

4.1. Results of an educational micro-research study

Respondents were selected from the following socio-professional categories (*Item 1*): parent/ legal guardian – 45; teacher – 25; community representative/ NGO member – 9; school principal/ administrator – 5; other role – 3. The majority of respondents were parents or legal guardians (52.3 %), providing the data with a perspective predominantly centered on the family environment. Teachers

represented the second largest group (28.7 %), followed by community and NGO representatives (10.3 %). School principals and administrators accounted for a relatively small proportion of respondents (5.7 %), reflecting the more limited involvement of decision-makers in completing the research instruments.

For *Item 2*, the respondents indicated the educational level of the child or class they currently interact with: preschool (kindergarten) – 12; primary education (preparatory class to 4th grade) – 30; lower secondary education (5th–8th grade) – 32; upper secondary/ vocational education – 13. It may therefore be observed that primary and lower secondary education together account for 70.1% of respondents, indicating a stronger mobilization of the educational community around the foundational stages of schooling. Preschool and upper secondary levels display approximately equal proportions (around 14–15%), reflecting the continuous interest of families across all stages of educational development.

Item 3 reflects the distribution of the sample according to three proposed residential areas: urban, rural, and peri-urban. The sample is dominated by respondents from urban areas ($n = 50$, approximately 57.5 %), followed by respondents from rural areas ($n = 25$, approximately 28.7 %) and peri-urban areas ($n = 12$, approximately 13.8 %). This structure allows for relevant comparisons between educational contexts characterized by different resources and community dynamics.

Item 4 measured, on a five-point Likert scale, the frequency of communication with the school outside mandatory meetings (1 = never: 8 %; 2 = rarely: 17 %; 3 = occasionally: 31 %; 4 = frequently: 29 %; 5 = weekly: 15 %). The following statistical values were obtained (Table 1):

Table 1. Frequency of communication with the school (scale 1–5)

Mean (M)	3,26
Standard Deviation (SD)	1,12
Modal Value	3 – Occasional (31 %)
Respondens with scores ≥ 4	44 (50,6 %)

The mean value of 3.26 indicates a moderate frequency of communication, situated between occasional and frequent interaction. Half of the respondents (50.6 %) reported frequent or very frequent communication with the school, representing a positive indicator of involvement. Nevertheless, one quarter of the sample (25 %) rarely or never communicates with the school outside the formal framework, highlighting a deficit in active engagement.

Regarding communication channels (*Item 5* – multiple-response item), the study identified the methods most frequently used by respondents. Percentages exceed 100 % because participants were allowed to select multiple options. The communication channels selected (in order of preference) were: WhatsApp/Messenger groups; face-to-face meetings; telephone calls/ SMS messages; school applications; e-mail; correspondence notebooks; and social media platforms. The

collected data indicate that instant messaging groups (WhatsApp and Messenger) constitute the most widely used communication channel (78.2 %), surpassing even face-to-face meetings (72.4 %). Specialized school applications are used by 41.4 % of respondents, suggesting a partial adoption of dedicated digital platforms. E-mail and correspondence notebooks—more traditional communication tools—remain relevant for approximately one quarter of the sample.

Concerning satisfaction with the quality of communication (*Item 6*), the mean score of 3.42 reflects a moderate to good level of satisfaction. Approximately half of the respondents (50.6 %) reported being satisfied or very satisfied with the quality of communication, while nearly one respondent out of five (18.4 %) expressed clear dissatisfaction (1 – Not at all satisfied = 5 %; 2 – Slightly satisfied = 13%; 3 – Moderately satisfied = 32 %; 4 – Satisfied = 35 %; 5 – Very satisfied = 15 %). The following statistical values were obtained from the data above (Table 2).

Table 2. Level of satisfaction in communication with the school

Mean (M)	3,42
Standard Deviation (SD)	1,01
Satisfied Respondents (≥ 4)	49,4 %
Dissatisfied Respondents (≤ 2)	17,2 %

The positively skewed distribution suggests the existence of a solid foundation of appreciation, while also indicating a significant segment requiring further improvement.

Item 7 refers to the existence of joint projects between schools and community organizations (yes, frequently = 18%; yes, occasionally = 37%; rarely = 29%; no/ do not know = 16%). Only 18.4% of respondents stated that frequent collaborative projects exist between schools and community organizations. Most participants reported occasional collaboration (36.8%) or rare collaboration (28.7%), while 16.1% indicated that such projects either do not exist or that they are unaware of them. These findings suggest that community partnerships remain at an incipient stage, lacking both systematic organization and sufficient visibility. Local communities possess valuable human resources, material support, and expertise capable of contributing significantly to the educational process. Formalizing collaborations through an annual calendar of activities could enhance both their visibility and impact.

Item 8 focused on preferred partnership activities. Respondents selected the types of activities they considered most useful (multiple-response item): career guidance programs = 69 %; joint cultural events = 65 %; visits to local institutions = 62 %; volunteering activities = 58 %; ecological projects = 48 %; camps and excursions = 44%; sponsorships/ donations = 31%. The highest level of interest was generated by career guidance programs (69 %) and joint cultural events (65.5 %), both categories having a direct impact on students' development. Visits to local

institutions and volunteering activities were also appreciated by more than half of the respondents. Sponsorships and donations, although materially useful, were perceived as the least important form of partnership (31 %), suggesting that respondents value active involvement more highly than financial support.

The degree of local community involvement was evaluated through *Item 9* (1 = not involved at all; 2 = slightly involved; 3 = moderately involved; 4 = involved; 5 = very involved). The obtained values are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Perception of the degree of community involvement

Mean (M)	2,92
Standard Deviation (SD)	1,08
Respondents with Scores ≤ 2	35,6 %
Respondents with Scores ≥ 4	29,9 %

The mean score of 2.92 reflects a general perception of low to moderate community involvement. More than one third of respondents (35.6%) considered community participation to be weak or nonexistent, while only 29.9% perceived the community as involved or highly involved. These results are consistent with responses to the previous item regarding the rarity of joint projects.

The questionnaire also identified potential obstacles in school–family–community collaboration (*Item 10*, multiple-response item). The main obstacles identified were: lack of time = 71 %; insufficient communication = 63 %; disinterest/low motivation = 55 %; limited financial resources = 48 %; lack of digital platforms = 42 %; mutual distrust = 33 %; geographical distance = 21 %. Lack of time was the most frequently cited obstacle (71.3 %), followed by insufficient communication (63.2 %) and disinterest or low motivation (55.2 %). Financial constraints were mentioned by nearly half of the respondents (48.3 %), while mutual distrust—although less frequently identified—was reported by one third of the sample (33.3 %), indicating a relational climate issue that requires particular attention.

Regarding the perceived importance of educational partnerships among school, family, and community (*Item 11*), responses were quantified through the following statistical data (Table 4).

Table 4. Perceived importance of partnerships for academic success

Mean (M)	4,04
Standard Deviation (SD)	0,91
Respondents with Scores ≥ 4	75,9 %
Respondents with Scores = 5	37,9 %

The mean score of 4.04—the highest recorded throughout the questionnaire—indicates a broad consensus regarding the value of educational partnerships. A total of 75.9 % of respondents considered such partnerships important or essential for students' academic success, while nearly 38 % assigned the maximum score. These findings provide a strong motivational foundation for implementing more structured and sustainable partnership strategies.

Regarding the suggestions formulated by respondents (*Item 12*), these focused on: the digitalization of communication (integrated platforms, school mobile applications, automated notifications), regular community events (annual activity calendars, school festivals open to the community), parent training programs (parenting workshops, parent schools, communication courses), involvement of local authorities (collaboration protocols, dedicated budgets, co-financed projects), transparency and feedback mechanisms (periodic reports, satisfaction questionnaires, general meetings).

The open-ended suggestions confirm and complement the quantitative data: respondents did not merely identify existing problems but also proposed concrete solutions centered on digitalization, continuity, and training. The high frequency of suggestions regarding digital platforms (38%) is consistent with the widespread use of instant messaging communication, indicating the need to transform informal practices into institutionalized systems.

4.2. Validation of the hypotheses

The conducted micro-research study generated a set of data/ results whose quantitative and qualitative interpretation validates the proposed hypotheses. The research purpose and objectives were also largely achieved.

The theoretical considerations presented alongside the data collected through the questionnaire outline a complex picture of the family–school–community partnership, characterized by several major tendencies that may be generalized as future directions for action and intervention:

- There is a declared willingness to collaborate, reflected in high scores regarding the importance of partnerships, which has not yet been fully translated into systematic practices.
- Communication is predominantly informal and digital (especially through WhatsApp), offering advantages related to rapidity while also presenting risks concerning traceability and confidentiality.
- Community involvement is perceived as insufficient and sporadic, contrasting with the needs identified by respondents.
- Lack of time and deficient communication remain the principal obstacles, which may be addressed through digitalization and procedural simplification.
- There is a clear convergence between open-ended suggestions and quantitative findings, increasing the internal validity of the research instrument.

Authentic partnerships between family and school involve mutual respect, open communication, and a shared orientation toward the child's well-being. The development of an effective partnership requires permanent communication, reciprocal respect, and the active involvement of all participants. Joint activities

contribute to the development of social competencies, the prevention of school-related difficulties, and the establishment of trust-based relationships between families and educational institutions.

5. Conclusions

Based on the findings obtained, several directions for future action are recommended: the implementation of integrated digital platforms for school–family–community communication, the development of annual partnership activity calendars, the organization of training sessions for parents and teachers regarding effective collaboration, and the establishment of formal partnership protocols with institutions and organizations within the local community.

The essence of an authentic partnership does not reside in the number of activities conducted, but rather in the quality of the relationships that are built: relationships based on mutual respect, open communication, shared responsibility, and a common vision centered on the child’s well-being. Regardless of the specific form it takes, an authentic educational partnership begins with a fundamental question: what can we accomplish together that we could not achieve separately?

The collective answer to this question, developed by all actors within the educational community, represents the most authentic source of pedagogical innovation and local social cohesion. Concrete partnership practices become effective when they are participatively planned, consistently implemented, transparently evaluated, and publicly celebrated - thus transforming partnership from a formal obligation into a living institutional culture.

In conclusion, students’ educational success depends to a significant extent on the collaboration among family, school, and community. By strengthening this partnership, favorable conditions may be created for the formation of responsible, autonomous individuals who are successfully integrated into society.

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